

Coatings for Industrial Heritage Surfaces– between the poles of aesthetics and durability

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Introduction

In Germany, outstanding basic industrial sites are increasingly being classified as monuments, as part of the progressive process of de-industrialisation. Some of these monuments, like the Zollverein Mining Complex in Essen, the Völklinger Hütte and the Rammelsberg mine in Goslar, have even been inscribed as world cultural heritage sites. It was never foreseen, however, that industrial sites should have a permanent life. Thus the wish to preserve the architectural evidence of the industrial age and to present it to the general public has given rise to new challenges, especially in the area of restoration and conservation. One of the major challenges is how to treat iron and steel components which have been exposed to the vagaries of the weather and are therefore at risk from heavy corrosion. This paper will present a brief outline of the conception and results of research to date on the assessment of coating systems.

Research approaches to transparent corrosion protection

Standard concepts on repairing major industrial sites consist of drastic measures to clean and treat corroded metal surfaces. These range from a complete removal of the old coatings and layers of corrosion to exposing naked metal surfaces, and their subsequent coating with a multilayered pigmented paint system. The processes have been technically matured and generally established. That said, they fundamentally change the appearance of the treated surface and lead – as intended – to a new surface (with a high potential for protecting the metal beneath from renewed corrosion). Starting from a conservation point of view, some may consider that there should be limits to such measures when working on monument objects. But we have to differentiate different cases. In the times of industrial operation many surfaces had a regular coating of protective paint, as was foreseen and implemented as a method of protection. These areas may be protected in the same way when the object changes to the monument state. For other areas of industrial monuments, where the "original" surface (as it appeared in its historical working context) has to be preserved in addition to effective corrosion protection, there exists a wish for "transparent" conservation.

A series of comprehensive studies has been made on the use of transparent coating materials, in two major research projects: These are 1) "Korrosionsschutz für umweltgeschädigte Industriedenkmäler aus Eisen und Stahl" (1996 - 1999) and 2) „A comparison of conservation materials and strategies for sustainable exploitation of industrial heritage made of iron and steel - CONSIST“ (2005 – 2008). Alongside standard commercial, purely organic products (oils, waxes, transparent paints) a new group of materials has moved to the centre of research interests of DBM. At the Fraunhofer Institute for Silicate Research in Würzburg: namely, inorganic-organic hybrid polymers (ORMOCERe¹, Mottner 2006) were developed and tested for coating purposes together with the DBM. Studies have been divided into two major areas: time accelerated laboratory tests and field trials on selected objects.

¹ Marke der Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V., München

Laboratory studies

Accelerated tests in laboratories are a good way of selecting suitable polymer coating materials from a huge range of possible products. Special sheet-metal samples, part of which have been artificially corroded in advance and treated with diverse transparent protective materials are deliberately exposed to simulated industrial and condensation atmospheres in climate chambers. Routine evaluations are then used to assess what remains of the coatings and the amount of new corrosion. Other additional major sources of knowledge included in the studies are the appearance of the coating and the remaining transparency. In the future it is intended to devote further investment to methods of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and optical image analysis systems.

Laboratory tests have shown that one of the most important decisive factors in coating iron and steel surfaces is the thickness of the layers of the conservation material. Thin coating layers are not sufficient to provide an effective protection from corrosion on steel samples e.g. in the case of a single coating of wax (this is also standard with other materials), but also in coatings of only ~ 10 µm, as achieved by a single application of spray or a manual application with a paint brush of low viscous ORMOCERs. It has been shown that an increase in the amount of the material used (a higher concentration in the solution, plus several applications equals a thicker layer of coating) is a decisive parameter for effective protection. Applying transparent inorganic pigments like glass tinsel can raise the level of thickness, and thereby the effectiveness of the protection. All in all, laboratory tests have yielded the following basic conclusions:

- The anticorrosive waxes which were tested are just as effective in protecting metals as transparent lacquers. Indeed, a few of them are even somewhat superior. This statement must be qualified because there have been no simulations of exposure to sunlight or continual rainfall. Both these realistic factors might lead to different evaluations.
- When comparing wax to lacquer, results have shown that the optical appearance of wax – a matt, unobtrusive surface – is superior.
- It is not possible to establish a pecking order in the case of anticorrosive waxes (waxes with added corrosion inhibitors), since the differences in quality are so slight, and are dependent on the test and the type of substrata.
- If we compare ORMOCERs with standard preferred lacquers (polyurethane systems), there are scarcely any differences.

Test surfaces on objects

All the promising products were subsequently tested on surfaces on model objects like the disused blast furnace site at the Henrichshütte steel works in Hattingen and the mineral processing plant at the Rammelsberg ore mine in Goslar. The main location for the studies has been the Henrichshütte. After almost 10 years exposure we are currently in a position to make the following summary (Conrads 2006):

- Transparent coatings are in no way a magic solution to the problem of protecting industrial monuments.
- All materials change the appearance of surfaces, even when they are transparent. A glossy appearance on services is an undesired side effect which can be quickly reduced by waxing.
- Transparent coating materials provide a temporary protection, even if periods of exposure are much shorter than with standard care systems.

- A careful, individual pre-treatment of surfaces (e.g. by a restorer) is very important, and may be decisive in terms of the durability of the coating. That said, because of the expense involved, such a procedure is very hard to implement when dealing with large areas on industrial monuments.
- The level of exposure to the weather concerning the areas to be protected is an important, if not to say decisive criterion when selecting coatings.
- In protected areas, waxes can easily compete with lacquers, the more so because they are much easier to "repair". When using waxes, those containing additional corrosion inhibitors are clearly more efficient than pure wax mixtures.
- Where surfaces are exposed to direct rainfall and strong sunshine, however, waxes deteriorate much more rapidly than paints.
- When talking about paints, at the moment the most durable coatings are polyurethane systems and ORMOCERs.
- The problem of lacquer systems (above all polyurethane) lies in the difficulty of removing them once more from the background, should this become necessary; and also in the subsequent re-treatment of the surface.
- Thus transparent coatings demand a high measure of responsibility from those responsible for the objects in order: a) to make the correct selection; and b) when considering the necessary conservation measures to be taken, right at the very start of operations.

Looking to the future

The performed studies have provided a good basis for assessing the various transparent coatings in respect of their suitability for protecting steel surfaces on listed buildings from corrosion. At the moment further studies are being conducted in a research project named CONSIST, in order to be able to judge the range of potential uses of transparent coatings. Here, beside the simple evaluation of the effectiveness and durability of the protection, the main features under consideration are the aesthetic aspect, their ability for further treatment, and the costs of the specific conservation measures. The use of pigmented systems with suitably matching colouring for rust areas is also being evaluated. It is only possible to provide a reliable result for the use of transparent coatings, when all these features have been considered.

Literature

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